

kringle containing transmembrane protein 1 (KREMEN1) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

kringle containing transmembrane protein 1(KREMEN1), encodes a high-affinity dickkopf homolog 1 (DKK1) transmembrane receptor that functionally cooperates with DKK1 to block wingless (WNT)/ β -catenin signaling. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 KREMEN1 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for KREMEN1-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

^{*}Time behavioural study of 3-odr KREMEN1 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3$ (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search done by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order KREMEN1 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination,

then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. kringle containing transmembrane protein 1 (KREMEN1)

Prothrombin, plasminogen, urokinase- and tissue- type plasminogen activators contain structures known as kringles. They correspond to autonomous structural and folding domains which mediate the binding of these multidomain proteins to other proteins. Patthy et al. [4] show that the amino acid sequences of the type II structures of the gelatin-binding region of fibronectin are homologous with those of the protease-kringles. Kringle domain, a triple loop, 3-disulfide bridge structure, is conserved in diverse proteins which play important roles in various biological processes.

Nakamura et al. [5] cloned KREMEN, a novel member of kringle-containing proteins, which is likely to be a type-I transmembrane protein composed of 473 amino acid residues. KREMEN has a kringle domain, a WSC domain, and CUB domains in the extracellular region, while the intracellular region has no conserved motif involved in signal transduction. Increased KREMEN mRNA levels in mouse embryo and its expression in the adult mouse in a variety of tissues suggested a potential role for KREMEN in the regulation of cellular responses upon extracellular stimulus or cell-cell interaction in neuronal and/or muscle cells.

Canonical WNT signalling via β -catenin pathway is transduced by two receptor families - Frizzled (FZD) proteins and lipoprotein-receptor-related proteins 5 and 6 (LRP-5/6) which bind WNTs and transmit their signal by stabilizing intracellular β -catenin. However, this pathway is inhibited by the secreted protein Dickkopf1 (DKK1) by binding to and antagonizing LRP-5/6. Mao et al. [6] show that the transmembrane proteins KREMEN-1/2 are high-affinity DKK1 receptors that cooperate with DKK1 to block WNT/ β -catenin signalling.

Upon binding to DKK1, KREMEN proteins (both KREMEN-1/2) are recruited into a complex with LRP-5/6, which leads to rapid endocytosis and removal of LRP-5/6 from the plasma membrane. This formation of a ternary complex composed of KREMEN, DKK, and LRP-5/6 (the coreceptor of WNT) inhibits WNT/ β -catenin signalling. The inhibitory function of DKKs depends on the presence of appropriate KREMEN proteins. Nakamura et al. [7] present the identification and structure of KREMEN, KREMEN as a negative regulator in WNT signalling, expression of KREMEN and its role in development and its involvement in WNT signalling and cancer.

I present 3rd order combinations of KREMEN1 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [8]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [8].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one

recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7_1C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a

strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 KREMEN1-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [9]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [10] and martinez implementation in Martinez [11] and Baudin et al. [12]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested KREMEN1-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving KREMEN1 were obtained from a full set of ${}^7C_3 = 350$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

NOTE - It is important to note that KERMEN1 along with DKK1 and LRP-5/6 were downregulated (*-ive* value) during the first half of the WNT3A stimulation in Gujral and MacBeath [1].

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of DKK1-KREMEN1-X combinations

Based on the above literature, KREMEN1 is known to interact with DKK1 to inhibit the WNT signaling pathway. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following com-

RANKING @ t_1 USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	96	24278	50801	44288	10781	AES-AXIN1-KREMEN1	127	47825	39191	53628	788
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2B	170	28253	38493	15670	30910	DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	178	24966	37758	33223	9256
FOXN1-KREMEN1-PPP2R1A	187	38390	45372	22596	7296	FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT3	217	53012	56130	3088	18960
CCND1-CTBP1-KREMEN1	234	57106	44293	35945	33357	CTNNB1P1-JUN-KREMEN1	241	6571	55388	29592	14471
FOXN1-KREMEN1-LRP5	260	52346	51858	34049	42979	F5H8-FZD2-KREMEN1	286	34277	55693	24595	31187
FBXW11-FOXN1-KREMEN1	302	14589	4660	6330	19835	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-SFRP4	362	833	2893	48271	49787
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	390	10815	10745	12917	12924	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	445	18545	22047	46724	18178
DKK1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	480	13941	53110	3917	4043	CTNNB1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	484	1965	14838	7676	28339
FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP4	510	51802	54641	8830	39747	FZD5-FOXN1-KREMEN1	511	1786	8577	7989	16170
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	529	10037	50110	50880	28493	FZD1-FZD7-KREMEN1	651	16749	42649	57051	9750
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT4	693	6753	23243	1864	44869	FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	742	14009	6113	8523	21187
CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	758	28255	42529	10768	13750	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	775	7975	18477	6845	18012
FZD5-GSK3A-KREMEN1	798	32935	3687	34447	2546	CCND1-FGF4-KREMEN1	833	56773	18833	37224	15499
FZD8-GSK3A-KREMEN1	914	37178	3268	52107	6645	F5H8-GSK3A-KREMEN1	921	38254	26495	28443	3064
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	939	687	5376	7847	13303	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP1	985	42401	54457	12806	414
DVL2-FGF4-KREMEN1	1025	11180	25345	35577	33719	FZD5-CCND2-KREMEN1	1049	44629	22542	28884	49843
KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	1055	20253	16697	487	37387	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	1064	30070	1340	20277	52737
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	1122	3656	11331	13933	38262	DKK1-FGF4-KREMEN1	1129	19854	18903	14425	19943
CSNK1G1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	1221	5094	21366	17954	17531	FZD1-FZD2-KREMEN1	1236	35400	37152	3827	42898
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	1239	30116	44329	46230	30098	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT4	1280	5994	3234	2746	2189
APC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1292	17817	5446	51090	6601	KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	1377	25809	2588	12830	26801
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	1377	25809	2588	12830	26801	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT2B	1400	34496	34759	43275	20181
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT2B	1401	36444	47192	17886	28451	KREMEN1-NKD1-SEN2	1463	18745	6060	20808	42111
FZD5-FZD2-KREMEN1	1552	30795	21588	5315	28264	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	1571	14622	52390	27682	7035
KREMEN1-RHOU-TCF7	1573	55772	27141	223	46704	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-WNT2B	1585	14425	197	53141	37098
FRZB-FZD2-KREMEN1	1603	3863	36101	9766	48273	EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1	1620	7884	6802	739	13419
CSNK1G1-CTNNB1-KREMEN1	1675	48319	35467	28250	6432	KREMEN1-NKD1-TCF7L1	1699	28241	2070	41242	30439
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	1727	6226	28247	11263	35521	FZD1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1738	40748	5530	55553	1476
KREMEN1-MYC-SEN2	1739	20338	4422	34221	40748	CTNNB1P1-FZD2-KREMEN1	1837	23176	37249	4014	33708
FBXW11-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1865	56429	31282	41254	1352	DAAMI-JUN-KREMEN1	1890	51281	41166	36350	16680
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2	1894	42716	55280	13922	40195	KREMEN1-PORCN-TCF7L1	1902	38888	15726	2313	30252
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	1937	45988	42307	30915	9629	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	1948	42829	14565	52294	56300
APC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2000	4298	6205	6426	23498	DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	2010	2457	38608	53030	25504
FZD5-FGF4-KREMEN1	2013	27018	21260	27088	23655	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT2B	2036	35623	4394	5538	18503
KREMEN1-FBXW4-WNT3A	2114	13176	100	22815	19325	DAAMI-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2129	51563	36659	50263	21382
FZD6-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2225	27912	27936	52258	25906	FBXW2-FGF4-KREMEN1	2253	32946	50021	47804	26837
CTBP1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2271	26478	2298	49251	1887	AES-DVL1-KREMEN1	2316	39410	26030	52356	23834
KREMEN1-F-WNT2B	2344	47077	5424	49942	15572	KREMEN1-PORCN-SFRP4	2368	33549	23605	2332	43954
CTBP1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2451	10517	9466	7533	49640	KREMEN1-MYC-TLE2	2509	13737	10240	55345	25198
FBXW2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2527	40868	10027	47061	40112	KREMEN1-LRP6-TCF7	2533	55286	41418	32082	2935
DAAMI-FGF4-KREMEN1	2579	47103	51872	50968	4413	KREMEN1-NKD1-TLE2	2619	18016	16139	44657	37610
APC-BTRC-KREMEN1	2657	22730	7427	25126	52825	FZD5-CCND1-KREMEN1	2661	25140	10521	9081	26597
KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT3A	2675	23678	2816	47552	40285	CCND3-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2685	41560	9399	7692	43041
BTRC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2723	18292	12669	9692	56435	FBXW2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2728	8404	19667	17910	51326
KREMEN1-WF1-WNT3A	2762	721	11586	56871	31145	KREMEN1-WNT3-WNT3A	2788	47193	12084	27016	19027
FZD1-JUN-KREMEN1	2822	32928	46013	50199	15289	DKK1-FZD2-KREMEN1	2860	30210	53732	5383	20250
CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	2872	42910	42232	51357	48270	CSNK1G1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	2889	6171	37322	13856	5323
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	2904	37451	19332	29917	48436	FZD7-JUN-KREMEN1	2975	27209	49555	48377	22318
AXIN1-DVL1-KREMEN1	3005	6666	41605	52750	7478	BTRC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3010	54393	56679	45265	52103
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3017	11044	1525	53908	3915	KREMEN1-NKD1-FBXW4	3108	22301	16832	29059	23025
KREMEN1-LRP6-SEN2	3111	32111	14514	33645	6872	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1	3159	39744	45905	6948	40383
FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3217	49686	3676	49905	14302	FBXW11-FGF4-KREMEN1	3258	55985	54859	34318	13486
FZD8-JUN-KREMEN1	3275	44731	52219	20333	8524	FBXW11-JUN-KREMEN1	3339	52289	38426	40741	34907
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3347	13841	2607	50326	30275	CCND2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	3355	3908	6975	5408	46170
DVL1-EP300-KREMEN1	3366	29392	28100	54892	20990	KREMEN1-MYC-WNT3A	3433	19129	6220	28682	38858
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	3542	41044	29584	5685	51990	KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1-WNT3A	3580	17181	25435	54188	25643
KREMEN1-PORCN-FBXW4	3663	26907	15869	622	32460	FBXW2-JUN-KREMEN1	3735	35906	54609	50369	55231
KREMEN1-PORCN-TCF7	3746	56109	39312	3880	34922	CSNK1G1-CTNNB1P1-KREMEN1	3759	25578	23550	7886	28116
KREMEN1-LRP6-FBXW4	3766	33137	25609	45562	1844	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	3796	45394	51834	52960	6499
KREMEN1-MYC-TCF7L1	3819	32963	15399	45595	28737	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT4	3871	11426	4535	41285	47213
CTNNB1-FGF4-KREMEN1	3963	19788	15003	22803	26132	CTBP2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3981	56103	1110	40270	1391
KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE2	4003	29172	18083	3949	32896	KREMEN1-T-TCF7L1	4058	45731	11965	33080	25646
KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT5A	4086	1014	15715	19712	13437	KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE1	4111	17653	11096	399	32135

Table 1: Rankings of KREMEN1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

binations for DKK1 along with KREMEN1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DKK1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, DKK1-FGF4-KREMEN1 and DKK1-FZD2-KREMEN1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	14265	7847	49848	50707	31671	AES-AXIN1-KREMEN1	37703	35313	40516	18682	15851
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2B	20404	27973	36396	884	30778	DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	13103	30709	32743	48017	27397
FOXN1-KREMEN1-PPP2R1A	21547	15130	581	7154	55001	FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT3	13156	54946	25548	2636	21279
CCND1-CTBP1-KREMEN1	28942	57047	8671	40620	6175	CTNNB1-JUN-KREMEN1	49360	1571	43983	55548	30690
FOXN1-KREMEN1-LRP5	11126	50667	3123	17750	44144	FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1	5444	42081	8565	25988	38407
FBXW11-FOXN1-KREMEN1	332	11091	39492	5306	3719	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-SFRP4	19893	13395	43502	13961	6355
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	7103	1710	43024	36832	31611	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	4639	142	27356	54948	19911
DKK1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	881	21837	24344	36049	9457	CTNNB1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	3133	5700	50426	39968	6394
FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP4	21541	47835	13452	25040	38289	FZD5-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2473	6345	54537	47495	8093
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	2147	22653	25065	18882	43497	FZD1-FZD7-KREMEN1	40446	14016	820	47659	32313
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT4	4572	591	18551	4045	46258	FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2901	4767	41791	45598	13163
CTNNB1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	23718	42906	43026	55168	47523	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	393	11453	41930	49554	21564
FZD5-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3906	30061	53828	42745	53934	CCND1-FGF4-KREMEN1	22424	56825	8471	20861	15165
FZD8-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1348	36579	51609	22398	40701	FSHB-GSK3A-KREMEN1	9218	45608	28535	37479	51895
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	3184	5794	52693	37317	689	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP1	27973	46263	7809	24618	51572
DVL2-FGF4-KREMEN1	6004	6605	12570	48822	49957	FZD5-CCND2-KREMEN1	8697	44124	49389	52728	52529
KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	2897	40815	14540	5841	26554	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	7864	26771	50128	43544	15239
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	3060	1922	41865	30003	8137	DKK1-FGF4-KREMEN1	1554	26908	3678	42614	56156
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	10123	4733	30223	55392	43989	FZD1-FZD2-KREMEN1	10931	27613	9671	42642	45433
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	12312	33122	8653	27029	51700	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT4	2412	6480	36977	30144	18633
APC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	127	26706	52155	45367	53973	KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	8946	29482	33980	6745	37128
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	8946	29482	33980	6745	37128	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT2B	10715	45017	15095	25349	17172
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT2B	4060	34624	13586	33545	46659	KREMEN1-NKD1-SEN2	730	3287	51067	20876	22424
FZD5-FZD2-KREMEN1	17381	29667	40888	35883	46791	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	6491	2240	25073	41585	18357
KREMEN1-RHOU-TCF7	13632	56061	32578	2640	36177	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-WNT2B	25164	28694	34566	35971	17687
FRZB-FZD2-KREMEN1	9733	3875	18132	24675	50396	EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2486	110	54841	38583	4454
CSNK1G1-CTNNB1-KREMEN1	12259	40883	18405	45871	37363	KREMEN1-NKD1-TCF7L1	6544	33167	55781	7544	9258
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	14683	17223	32337	21120	1723	FZD1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1383	26847	53461	44646	50340
KREMEN1-MYC-SEN2	7375	12701	49420	6987	13204	CTNNB1-FZD2-KREMEN1	10840	35951	31211	40651	41730
FBXW11-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2846	54984	50753	24803	36268	DAAM1-JUN-KREMEN1	12541	51560	9266	55905	3551
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2	14202	42807	982	1807	50203	KREMEN1-PORCN-TCF7L1	5105	42564	13754	28956	27851
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	5995	44498	42143	51675	21496	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	1514	40573	41207	46205	49688
APC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	1997	6943	51297	49623	30810	DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	28857	3	41815	56574	3054
FZD5-FGF4-KREMEN1	1921	28429	50401	52865	52795	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT2B	7206	28407	30386	2208	20264
KREMEN1-FBXW4-WNT3A	49105	7228	49337	28152	8690	DAAM1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2003	53652	54181	54441	24386
FZD6-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2997	31223	53428	45556	33165	FBXW2-FGF4-KREMEN1	2821	26088	13154	23517	16921
CTBP1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1319	10146	55450	49855	53098	AES-DVL1-KREMEN1	23959	30765	28010	19926	10756
KREMEN1-3-WNT2B	5079	45857	6720	48287	28414	KREMEN1-PORCN-SFRP4	1803	22519	801	35021	39778
CTBP1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	5743	17110	49946	41629	26263	KREMEN1-MYC-TLE2	15234	1306	52625	36242	22622
FBXW2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	852	35836	33828	33146	22194	KREMEN1-LRP6-TCF7	3639	53069	30894	20591	19675
DAAM1-FGF4-KREMEN1	870	48494	7124	51889	10006	KREMEN1-NKD1-TLE2	2919	14915	47965	33551	33612
APC-BTRC-KREMEN1	8265	27604	37492	52851	54717	FZD5-CCND1-KREMEN1	9857	36236	47155	44679	56118
KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT3A	9700	7837	52991	45907	10853	CCND3-FOXN1-KREMEN1	1171	34063	53094	50272	4611
BTRC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2135	23342	46688	49929	2379	FBXW2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	1595	364	52793	37705	895
KREMEN1-WIF1-WNT3A	38760	4243	33739	39807	7207	KREMEN1-WNT3-WNT3A	13113	51425	51324	32502	6247
FZD1-JUN-KREMEN1	15931	13787	9034	41845	30091	DKK1-FZD2-KREMEN1	6261	35724	3154	16366	45481
CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	3201	51583	32100	52166	52493	CSNK1G1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	16581	39296	9396	40247	34672
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	2480	27771	5674	47549	30280	FZD7-JUN-KREMEN1	6606	12101	29205	53157	12973
AXIN1-DVL1-KREMEN1	6881	8114	22985	56273	14578	BTRC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	5140	53781	54895	53606	19024
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	5655	3612	51883	54394	46466	KREMEN1-NKD1-FBXW4	16975	10848	31634	30290	26950
KREMEN1-LRP6-SEN2	2434	29765	40575	33866	40506	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1	14501	25331	8315	26659	34832
FRAT1-FGF4-KREMEN1	1014	49731	56438	48125	38195	FBXW11-FGF4-KREMEN1	3698	53770	4230	517	36721
FZD8-JUN-KREMEN1	8991	45182	43032	29768	21965	FBXW11-JUN-KREMEN1	8267	48029	13598	24626	10882
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	962	5165	52201	49330	13895	CCND2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	8379	10719	51570	46577	14647
DVL1-EP300-KREMEN1	54034	12200	13668	57031	15029	KREMEN1-MYC-WNT3A	10637	5567	56637	35572	1429
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	9306	45373	50696	51816	46911	KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1-WNT3A	5894	4234	35325	31271	14229
KREMEN1-PORCN-FBXW4	2024	24361	7927	6273	32503	FBXW2-JUN-KREMEN1	45460	39448	22654	30792	5213
KREMEN1-LRP6-TCF7	4135	52520	18227	7012	25650	CSNK1G1-CTNNB1-KREMEN1	44820	20207	8775	44692	55891
KREMEN1-MYC-FBXW4	4459	21512	25267	25628	35821	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	46085	42522	27876	8199	46619
KREMEN1-MYC-TCF7L1	11844	48709	41046	17332	2258	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT4	1146	12492	44039	43786	11253
CTNNB1-FGF4-KREMEN1	1779	13542	31545	43294	49835	CTBP2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	2929	53064	51746	47070	37417
KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE2	18984	25116	9384	24961	48839	KREMEN1-T-TCF7L1	1217	40415	35163	33451	5680
KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT5A	4362	35794	22223	40251	36925	KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE1	12519	13926	4026	25562	26223

Table 2: Rankings of KREMEN1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of LRP-5/6-KREMEN1-X combinations

Since KREMEN proteins combine with DKK1 along with LRP-5/6, looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of LRP family along with KREMEN1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOXN1-KREMEN1-LRP5, KREMEN1-LRP6-SEN2, KREMEN1-LRP6-FBXW4 and KREMEN1-LRP6-TCF7. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a

RANKING @ t_1 USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	40950	45002	28772	48247	9854	AES-AXIN1-KREMEN1	15129	20699	60	19492	50134
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2B	48078	14775	45903	47094	15768	DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	30808	34898	33501	52840	6443
FOXN1-KREMEN1-PPP2R1A	42868	43393	35692	37283	25597	FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT3	22912	27457	7524	8198	32025
CCND1-CTBP1-KREMEN1	2059	53588	1909	4100	53006	CTNNBIP1-JUN-KREMEN1	42377	46499	47863	48423	9908
FOXN1-KREMEN1-LRP5	48531	10599	34009	31625	7563	FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1	36466	29558	45780	49639	2209
FBXW11-FOXN1-KREMEN1	36681	54148	38407	41684	18205	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-SFRP4	47389	38291	46157	33295	21478
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	12568	9848	1206	5693	56612	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	11605	22398	6349	16123	55238
DKK1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	49863	2268	35179	34070	52801	CTNNB1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	28350	28602	22304	4596	30984
FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP4	7110	32958	11953	11793	25861	FZD5-FOXN1-KREMEN1	40550	9655	41021	31346	25618
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	21369	16424	25622	19556	47905	FZD1-FZD7-KREMEN1	51823	19533	33033	29848	22214
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT4	2994	1634	5445	11732	52786	FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	5566	2122	4725	4323	49299
CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	2163	4891	11842	2940	40557	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	57030	55282	44745	35369	8120
FZD5-GSK3A-KREMEN1	16434	54131	7576	208	46476	CCND1-FGF4-KREMEN1	6300	54164	19681	18160	46828
FZD8-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1673	51151	25679	27789	20543	FSHB-GSK3A-KREMEN1	49626	22553	37390	51741	6459
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	21482	50446	17603	1664	40258	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP1	46908	27207	43387	43980	36486
DVL2-FGF4-KREMEN1	28296	6083	20156	19941	55458	FZD5-CCND2-KREMEN1	48984	49394	53174	47456	2995
KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	1460	11304	1074	20122	52679	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	52932	56977	53771	37472	14726
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	31821	16389	28671	30403	11306	DKK1-FGF4-KREMEN1	3925	2235	12144	2997	40109
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	22944	41262	26386	13278	43474	FZD1-FZD2-KREMEN1	15110	16794	24118	25653	14942
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	49711	51438	57107	44900	43052	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT4	15955	22656	18139	572	9093
APC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	22161	34336	12787	23677	7226	KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	36088	42706	41171	37942	19003
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	36088	42706	41171	37942	19003	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT2B	3720	31186	24394	8640	52443
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT2B	52764	52181	54179	55890	32504	KREMEN1-NKD1-SEN2	56836	50251	32521	51554	1744
FZD5-FZD2-KREMEN1	18555	33011	7751	196	40221	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	6923	4884	26325	13483	55790
KREMEN1-RHOU-TCF7	4926	18206	668	7937	52639	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-WNT2B	2599	25978	4343	22180	25119
FRZB-FZD2-KREMEN1	15195	18589	16392	489	7409	EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1	23162	5450	14335	12286	51032
CSNK1G1-CTNNB1-KREMEN1	8399	6622	8923	3958	38591	KREMEN1-NKD1-TCF7L1	584	45730	97	3743	56440
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	37975	14894	44042	43100	25518	FZD1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	7660	43808	24295	26443	39968
KREMEN1-MYC-SEN2	17023	9287	11185	185	42065	CTNNBIP1-FZD2-KREMEN1	10794	9878	11545	460	10405
FBXW11-GSK3A-KREMEN1	21461	3002	26958	4138	47620	DAAM1-JUN-KREMEN1	52625	28542	37711	31692	4937
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2	9044	42513	11318	10102	41349	KREMEN1-PORCN-TCF7L1	55719	32088	53306	30161	3431
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	40594	22021	35719	33231	5409	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	9212	1819	7168	7601	47095
APC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	29547	40708	55148	45215	3732	DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	460	53163	11120	19183	46244
FZD5-FGF4-KREMEN1	6216	5651	2403	7647	52951	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT2B	36576	35166	39887	54348	48410
KREMEN1-FBXW4-WNT3A	45167	47280	56590	48968	2663	DAAM1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	13384	15668	12158	498	56140
FZD6-GSK3A-KREMEN1	12895	32903	20439	2759	51190	FBXW2-FGF4-KREMEN1	22248	48690	8637	9586	46423
CTBP1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	26256	33539	19902	1842	38069	AES-DVL1-KREMEN1	22925	17355	8573	17311	25079
KREMEN1- β -WNT2B	7236	31182	12044	18634	52339	KREMEN1-PORCN-SFRP4	1575	45337	8949	23208	52407
CTBP1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	39964	20046	56465	43731	25806	KREMEN1-MYC-TLE2	45670	47473	48642	49391	21316
FBXW2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	25123	9865	17408	393	41917	KREMEN1-LRP6-TCF7	1727	7976	1357	1445	52140
DAAM1-FGF4-KREMEN1	7127	14101	26191	16548	35458	KREMEN1-NKD1-TLE2	15875	10503	2532	217	43597
APC-BTRC-KREMEN1	37985	37331	55282	41112	5158	FZD5-CCND1-KREMEN1	20691	21099	3090	417	50939
KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT3A	3850	55089	612	11917	55918	CCND3-FOXN1-KREMEN1	51128	56410	37630	41173	22159
BTRC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	50834	8273	50274	53098	8493	FBXW2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	31050	48418	48879	52531	24819
KREMEN1-WIF1-WNT3A	36608	31863	33558	56397	51574	KREMEN1-WNT3-WNT3A	46697	24784	33813	55605	41537
FZD1-JUN-KREMEN1	50807	8217	31011	33476	7864	DKK1-FZD2-KREMEN1	8878	48703	16689	25640	46207
CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	38479	27988	31220	33378	4766	CSNK1G1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	54343	4395	40167	51788	18755
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	49601	24278	44028	43212	12272	FZD7-JUN-KREMEN1	13407	6514	26939	4591	30820
AXIN1-DVL1-KREMEN1	14308	33186	25541	10671	49471	BTRC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	8824	50530	21375	2882	33323
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	52307	56531	47402	55645	3684	KREMEN1-NKD1-FBXW4	15922	39691	1142	12162	54069
KREMEN1-LRP6-SEN2	3201	51293	12356	14720	31932	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1	8920	18978	27908	10801	36087
FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	7872	42308	28346	8689	37391	FBXW11-FGF4-KREMEN1	23854	8666	12120	5305	31743
FZD8-JUN-KREMEN1	44256	39609	38215	56844	3545	FBXW11-JUN-KREMEN1	28638	40636	44640	48839	7440
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	56097	50759	42458	41643	27236	CCND2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	7182	3689	8117	4641	42356
DVL1-EP300-KREMEN1	53244	4343	43692	35471	20160	KREMEN1-MYC-WNT3A	53432	44377	45039	45412	2524
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	17526	25193	23946	23550	12450	KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1-WNT3A	7391	2325	5102	8894	56781
KREMEN1-PORCN-FBXW4	55579	11951	48161	33924	4762	FBXW2-JUN-KREMEN1	40033	20545	34038	56164	16905
KREMEN1-PORCN-TCF7	1434	24959	3863	27001	53818	CSNK1G1-CTNNBIP1-KREMEN1	28185	25608	21278	2355	52283
KREMEN1-LRP6-FBXW4	54867	1776	44391	39618	1479	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	29288	36103	39298	31122	2254
KREMEN1-MYC-TCF7L1	56751	50531	56726	45121	4763	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT4	53306	2099	56540	45244	1241
CTNNB1-FGF4-KREMEN1	52691	24612	41182	40890	28618	CTBP2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	22993	39974	5113	13082	37125
KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE2	54746	5958	46990	32840	4508	KREMEN1-T-TCF7L1	18200	10728	3144	4198	52427
KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT5A	41161	34326	39043	56585	47900	KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE1	2413	51146	10205	24334	52670

Table 3: Rankings of KREMEN1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of WNT-KREMEN1-X combinations

Since there is inhibition of the WNT signaling pathway due to presence of KREMEN activity (and vice versa), combinations of WNTs that might be getting inhibited via KREMEN1 could tell which WNT molecules are getting affected. Looking at the ta-

RANKING @ t_1 USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	50060	49716	44146	14490	16078	AES-AXIN1-KREMEN1	28064	7026	11453	39524	42223
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2B	21687	4778	50738	46118	18804	DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	35856	27962	6728	43550	27735
FOXN1-KREMEN1-PPP2R1A	9818	15093	45644	39058	38490	FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT3	36925	40473	11710	51127	46925
CCND1-CTBP1-KREMEN1	42157	8399	8751	25688	42625	CTNNB1-JUN-KREMEN1	18623	46010	5144	39503	49383
FOXN1-KREMEN1-LRP5	18720	14285	27556	23995	33506	FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1	45395	27154	3148	15559	7265
FBXW11-FOXN1-KREMEN1	45193	35978	856	882	52991	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-SFRP4	8033	44599	37769	50506	31645
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	4187	16379	10411	17376	49738	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	32750	6325	30769	2643	11537
DKK1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	10750	27873	12499	26591	19395	CTNNB1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	44655	43789	50547	9976	47585
FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP4	7114	42866	55853	44346	3242	FZD5-FOXN1-KREMEN1	9688	45351	53521	1084	18548
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	24857	20786	27757	39745	8714	FZD1-FZD7-KREMEN1	43574	40365	16466	8744	9258
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT4	25014	55908	56360	6264	40529	FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	6535	4193	12656	15365	2682
CTNNB1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	28588	7834	42573	50625	38323	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	57068	22013	50507	44487	22506
FZD5-GSK3A-KREMEN1	38767	22158	10974	23233	55027	CCND1-FGF4-KREMEN1	19916	51304	39724	4986	16639
FZD8-GSK3A-KREMEN1	17139	24546	27803	54652	25205	FSHB-GSK3A-KREMEN1	43085	48197	16908	5349	9023
DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	11078	11553	5133	32051	21036	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP1	16869	8888	49106	16150	24856
DVL2-FGF4-KREMEN1	16029	31782	36146	38636	37884	FZD5-CCND2-KREMEN1	38134	52353	1088	35667	23164
KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	53256	34131	37244	42862	23394	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	30698	50067	9324	3950	37622
CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	32146	2230	14527	12211	48112	DKK1-FGF4-KREMEN1	1421	22826	55080	35917	38433
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	34887	2984	15075	26075	37944	FZD1-FZD2-KREMEN1	38661	2657	53145	2205	37629
CSNK1G1-FGF4-KREMEN1	23388	19547	27651	18744	8543	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT4	2199	38104	48857	13973	4782
APC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	14661	25765	12588	14922	6100	KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	5432	49056	32287	41650	15766
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A	5432	49056	32287	41650	15766	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT2B	41860	50698	42188	13420	1100
KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT2B	25373	52290	22610	2903	12826	KREMEN1-NKD1-SEN2	36876	47876	34322	22045	9642
FZD5-FZD2-KREMEN1	40990	12269	19024	3117	5138	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	21900	17437	22609	16420	7910
KREMEN1-RHOU-TCF7	39316	49503	18837	54420	4274	KREMEN1-PPP2CA-WNT2B	36014	45601	55143	6929	4063
FRZB-FZD2-KREMEN1	8804	51812	29453	15852	40276	EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1	23284	7607	24950	49468	6281
CSNK1G1-CTNNB1-KREMEN1	7668	39456	50237	10228	44604	KREMEN1-NKD1-TCF7L1	47281	23426	24140	15351	37941
DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1	5296	33823	22412	27612	28817	FZD1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	16075	26322	11907	16976	52207
KREMEN1-MYC-SEN2	17	20569	8000	19943	10559	CTNNB1-FZD2-KREMEN1	33968	4007	8292	1357	23143
FBXW11-GSK3A-KREMEN1	19167	39549	15264	34669	748	DAAM1-JUN-KREMEN1	48712	41810	15310	24797	13617
FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2	45004	34538	42993	48072	47798	KREMEN1-PORCN-TCF7L1	55489	51329	54116	43728	32279
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	48706	41487	1000	47	11103	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	9910	50112	48782	5621	8051
APC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	36831	2796	35774	35884	51708	DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1	48918	4343	12297	8429	46878
FZD5-FGF4-KREMEN1	41522	25598	7931	26985	47216	KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT2B	9185	50045	47503	34240	14152
KREMEN1-FBXW4-WNT3A	8418	46509	36118	39983	9062	DAAM1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	7879	20599	27203	34991	30869
FZD6-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3749	39584	4701	9004	1185	FBXW2-FGF4-KREMEN1	29288	37147	42201	24033	12585
CTBP1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	50382	23649	10991	35546	51991	AES-DVL1-KREMEN1	41076	4127	16423	26303	21895
KREMEN1-T-WNT2B	7910	47660	18293	4580	6460	KREMEN1-PORCN-SFRP4	45360	26462	43370	7174	42299
CTBP1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	43104	1503	38616	42935	18900	KREMEN1-MYC-TLE2	7180	34833	40660	42701	20675
FBXW2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	32514	22442	29350	56335	23809	KREMEN1-LRP6-TCF7	45198	56569	20872	16353	4752
DAAM1-FGF4-KREMEN1	51285	45599	3582	54225	45866	KREMEN1-NKD1-TLE2	23720	51881	8553	12334	55039
APC-BTRC-KREMEN1	51514	22765	34066	39078	26946	FZD5-CCND1-KREMEN1	900	16752	27790	38913	7661
KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT3A	47109	46468	16075	12688	6199	CCND3-FOXN1-KREMEN1	26465	7808	38699	29756	14406
BTRC-FOXN1-KREMEN1	28736	20728	33589	46458	19066	FBXW2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	48470	2619	40052	46535	11071
KREMEN1-WIF1-WNT3A	6067	35361	30834	25461	23532	KREMEN1-WNT3-WNT3A	19008	54560	37296	5287	22527
FZD1-JUN-KREMEN1	53551	43597	19353	12885	13010	DKK1-FZD2-KREMEN1	13964	6704	6723	16262	45658
CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	16005	50884	46918	47316	11230	CSNK1G1-CTBP2-KREMEN1	53825	42416	31321	53750	13659
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	18735	48555	26440	4828	14893	FZD7-JUN-KREMEN1	5034	43389	45776	50895	332
AXIN1-DVL1-KREMEN1	11999	51310	52402	10539	6603	BTRC-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1807	43605	24019	2592	3552
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	7377	1898	35969	19960	56231	KREMEN1-NKD1-FBXW4	27950	22905	48525	6087	41176
KREMEN1-LRP6-SEN2	38083	51801	25209	6921	1953	FOXN1-KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1	49905	39981	18327	39308	39170
FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	13207	50057	16985	12076	1552	FBXW11-FGF4-KREMEN1	33510	17496	38891	6726	6249
FZD8-JUN-KREMEN1	20929	20816	18027	28440	15018	FBXW11-JUN-KREMEN1	17240	24815	1007	138	26081
DIXDC1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	34532	265	13430	34486	30125	CCND2-FOXN1-KREMEN1	24138	11510	34191	9154	8422
DVL1-EP300-KREMEN1	10232	7708	9155	50244	56618	KREMEN1-MYC-WNT3A	25654	54231	30951	12063	16864
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	27974	46025	36509	52732	2302	KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1-WNT3A	42884	32211	8455	56502	6413
KREMEN1-PORCN-FBXW4	53339	46924	14845	7839	25915	FBXW2-JUN-KREMEN1	8467	39307	47638	42224	56421
KREMEN1-LRP6-TCF7	17088	18928	28118	34188	36309	CSNK1G1-CTNNB1-KREMEN1	4990	37149	51721	2694	51762
KREMEN1-LRP6-FBXW4	22796	52381	49748	32966	13776	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	20293	34511	35279	44682	8912
KREMEN1-MYC-TCF7L1	47106	53083	36318	10618	16583	KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT4	16754	42641	37982	17345	22299
CTNNB1-FGF4-KREMEN1	34304	7797	36678	6913	44533	CTBP2-GSK3A-KREMEN1	47059	6932	53816	47837	19808
KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE2	23185	49752	30051	54929	27558	KREMEN1-T-TCF7L1	22734	55588	37873	56516	29210
KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT5A	8580	19453	28068	44618	42482	KREMEN1-PORCN-TLE1	55279	35702	32275	54148	505

Table 4: Rankings of KREMEN1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

bles above, one finds the following combinations for members of WNT family along with KREMEN1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2B, KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT4, KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A, KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT2B, FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2, KREMEN1-FBXW4-WNT3A, KREMEN1-T-WNT2B, KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT3A, KREMEN1-WIF1-WNT3A, KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B, KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT5A, FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT3, KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A,

KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT4, KREMEN1-PORCN-WNT3A, KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT2B, KREMEN1-PPP2CA-WNT2B, KREMEN1-WNT1-WNT2B, KREMEN1-WNT3-WNT3A, KREMEN1-MYC-WNT3A, KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1-WNT3A and KREMEN1-NKD1-WNT4. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of FZD-KREMEN1-X combinations

The initiation of the WNT signaling happens when WNT molecules form a ternary complex with FZD and LRP-5/6. Since there is inhibition of the WNT signaling pathway due to presence of KREMEN activity (and vice versa), combinations of FZDs along with the WNTs that might be getting inhibited via KREMEN1 could tell which FZD molecules are getting affected. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FZD family along with KREMEN1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1, FZD5-GSK3A-KREMEN1, FZD8-GSK3A-KREMEN1, FZD5-FZD2-KREMEN1, FRZB-FZD2-KREMEN1, DIXDC1-FZD2-KREMEN1, FZD5-FGF4-KREMEN1, FZD6-GSK3A-KREMEN1, FZD1-JUN-KREMEN1, CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1, FZD8-JUN-KREMEN1, FSHB-FZD2-KREMEN1, FZD5-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FZD1-FZD7-KREMEN1, FZD5-CCND2-KREMEN1, FZD1-FZD2-KREMEN1, FZD1-GSK3A-KREMEN1, CTNNBIP1-FZD2-KREMEN1, FZD5-CCND1-KREMEN1, DKK1-FZD2-KREMEN1 and FZD7-JUN-KREMEN1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of FOXN1-KREMEN1-X combinations

WNT signaling has been reported to regulate thymocyte proliferation and selection at several stages during T cell ontogeny, as well as the expression of FOXN1 in thymic epithelial cells (TECs). Osada et al. [13] used KREMEN1 knockout mice to examine KREMEN1 expression in the thymus and its function in thymocyte and TEC development. They observed that neonatal mice showed elevated expression of KREMEN1 in all TEC subsets. Further, KREMEN1^{-/-} mice exhibited a severe defect in thymic cortical architecture, including large epithelial free regions, while a TOPFlash assay revealed a 2-fold increase in canonical WNT signaling in TEC lines derived from KREMEN1^{-/-} mice, when compared with KREMEN1^{+/+} derived TEC lines. It can be inferred that knockout of KREMEN1 could have affected the expression of FOXN1. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for FOXN1 along with KREMEN1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2B, FOXN1-KREMEN1-PPP2R1A, FOXN1-KREMEN1-LRP5, FBXW11-FOXN1-KREMEN1, CSNK1G1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, DKK1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP4, DIXDC1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, CSNK1D-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT2, APC-FOXN1-KREMEN1, CTBP1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, BTRC-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FOXN1-KREMEN1-WNT3, CTNNB1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FZD5-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, CSNK2A1-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FOXN1-KREMEN1-SFRP1, EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1, CCND3-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FBXW2-FOXN1-KREMEN1, FOXN1-KREMEN1-SLC9A3R1 and CCND2-FOXN1-KREMEN1. All

these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.6. Examining the behaviour of JUN-KREMEN1-X combinations

Zhang et al. [14] investigated the effects of intrathecal injection of recombinant DKK3 (rDKK3) on mechanical allodynia and microglial activation in the spinal cord after spared nerve injury (SNI) in rats. They found that SNI induced a significant decrease in the levels of DKK3, KREMEN1 and DVL1, and upregulated the expression of phosphorylated apoptosis signal-regulating kinase 1 (p-ASK1), phosphorylated c-JUN N-terminal kinase (p-JNK), phosphorylated p38 (p-p38) in the spinal cord. c-JUN N-terminal kinases (JNKs) bind and phosphorylate c-JUN on Ser-63 and Ser-73 within its transcriptional activation domain. With respect to the recordings in the data by Gujral and MacBeath [1], KREMEN1 and DKK1 were downregulated, while JUN was upregulated, during the early phase of WNT3A stimulation. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for JUN along with KREMEN1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1, FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1, FZD1-JUN-KREMEN1, FZD8-JUN-KREMEN1, DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1, CTNNBIP1-JUN-KREMEN1, EP300-JUN-KREMEN1, CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1, DAAM1-JUN-KREMEN1, DIXDC1-JUN-KREMEN1, FZD7-JUN-KREMEN1, FBXW11-JUN-KREMEN1 and FBXW2-JUN-KREMEN1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of KREMEN1 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the KREMEN1, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For KREMEN1, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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